

EFFECTS OF DIFFERENT SLAUGHTERING METHODS ON MUSCLE PH AND BLOOD VARIABLES OF HETEROCLARIAS HYBRID FISH

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ABSTRACT

The effect of different slaughtering methods on muscle pH and blood variables of heteroclarias (*Heterobranchus bidorsalis* ♂ × *Clarias gariepinus* ♀) was studied. The experiment was a completely randomized design comprising four slaughtering methods: percussive stunning, salt stunning, ice asphyxia, and electroshock. Eight (8) kg of live catfish, *C. gariepinus*, with an average weight of 500 ± 21 g were collected from the concrete, they were divided into four groups and each group was slaughtered using various slaughtering methods including percussive stunning, salt stunning, ice slurry asphyxia and electroshock. The stress indicators (urea, glucose, sodium, chloride, potassium, osmolality, lactate and cortisol) were checked in the fish blood that was collected immediately after slaughter following standard experimental procedures. The muscle pH and rigor mortis were also measured. Fish stunned using percussive stunning had the highest pH (7.15) while that stunned with salt had a pH of 6.9. Glucose, cortisol and urea of heteroclarias slaughtered using ice slurry asphyxia was significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher than when other slaughtering methods were adopted. It is concluded that the various slaughtering methods impacted some stress on heteroclarias but ice slurry asphyxia impacted the most severe stress. However, the values obtained for the pH and blood variables in this study indicate that the fish is good for consumption irrespective of the slaughtering method employed.

Keywords: Slaughtering methods, muscle pH, blood variables and heteroclarias

INTRODUCTION

Hybridization is one of the successful techniques to achieve improved traits by crossing two different species or strains (Gashaw *et al.*, 2016). Hybridization through cross and selective breeding methods holds promise in boosting aquaculture production in Africa (Omeji *et al.*, 2013). The output of *Clarias* hybrid is increasing in Nigeria (Anetekhai, 2013). The culture of hybrid catfish (*Heterobranchus dorsalis*, ♂ × *Clarias gariepinus*, ♀) is now practiced by many

farmers in Nigeria due to the availability of the fish seed from many research institutions such as the African Regional Aquaculture Centre (ARAC) Aluu, Port Harcourt Rivers State Nigeria (Gabriel and Edori, 2010).

Fish pain is one of the reoccurring topics in fish welfare in recent times, (Sneddon *et al.*, 2003) stated that there is overwhelming evidence that suggests that fishes do feel pain much like humans because the reason why humans feel pain

is because man inherited pain receptors and associated cognitive toolbox from a fish ancestor. Robb and Krestin (2002) also stated that fishes do detect noxious stimuli and they respond to emotions i.e. fish cognitively engaged with pain. Raffaelina and Dario (2023) stated that killing animals may cause pain, distress, fear, or other forms of suffering to the animals themselves, even under the best available technical conditions. European Council (2009) recognized the fact that fishes are slaughtered slaughter in different contexts and they show physiological differences compared to terrestrial animals; it is therefore imperative as a welfare rule principle that they shall be spared any avoidable pain, distress, or suffering during their killing and related slaughtering operations (Boylard and Brooke, 2017). It is also a known fact that the extent of stress that fish pass through influences the quality of products obtainable from such fish (Ayelaja, 2019). There is a disagreement on whether fish feel pain or not as both sides of the argument set the same requirements for pain perception (Donald and Andrew, 2009). Concern about fish welfare at slaughter is becoming a major issue in the fisheries industry due to the need for good quality fish as raw material to produce good fish products, thus the need to establish adequate pre-slaughter/stunning procedures that will guarantee loss of consciousness and insensibility in fish before death (Van de Vis *et al.*, 2003). Improper pre-slaughter handling of fish sometimes leads to hypoxia in fish and the fish respond to hypoxic conditions by struggling to continue the provision of energy and oxygen to the brain (Donald and Andrew, 2009). Heteroclaris being a freshwater hybrid fish is not an exception as fresh water fish respond to hypoxic condition by increasing blood glucose as this supports the production of glycolytic adenosine triphosphate (ATP), which in turn increases cerebral blood flow through its vasodilation effects. Sorensen *et al.* (2004) stated that handling stress prior to slaughter may cause enormous physiological

responses that do complicate fish processing and influence the end product quality. Olsen *et al.* (2006) stated that physical activity and stress have a detrimental effect on bleeding. Soldatov (2006) conducted a study on fish blood flow under physical stress and observed that fish can redistribute the blood between organs and muscles and thus increase the blood content in the muscle. Stress was reported to have effects on the coagulation rate of fish blood, as the rate of coagulation increases as stress increases (Ruis and Bayne, 1997). A drop in the muscle pH of fish before killing is an indicator of pre-slaughter stress (Skjervold *et al.*, 2001). Erikson *et al.* (1997) and Sorensen *et al.* (2004) reported that the lowering of the pH as a result of stress in fish is due to the accumulation of H⁺ and lactic acid because ATP and glycogen stores are reduced, due to muscle activity. Normal muscle pH in a non-stressed Atlantic salmon was reported to be 7.4±0.1 (Olsen *et al.*, 2006). Acerete *et al.* (2009) stated that a major way to minimize fish suffering during slaughter is to use methods that make fish less sensitive to stressful procedures prior to the actual death. There are several stunning methods used in fish slaughter but there is no consensus on which method is least stressful for the fish. There is also paucity of information on the effect of different slaughtering methods on pain indices of the fish species. This study therefore investigated the effects of different slaughtering methods on muscle pH and blood variables of heteroclaris hybrid fish.

Materials and Methods

Ethical approval

Approval for the use of heteroclaris for this study was obtained from the Ethical Review Committee of the Department of Fisheries and Aquaculture, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Ilorin, Nigeria.

Sample collection

Eight kilogram (8 kg) of live heteroclaris fish (16 pieces) with an average weight of

500 ± 21g were collected from the concrete tank of a reputable fish farm within Ilorin metropolis Kwara State Nigeria at 6:45 am to reduce stress on the fish, they were conveyed using two 25 litres plastic bowls (8 fish in each bowl to reduce overcrowding which could lead to stress on the fish) within 43 min to the wet laboratory of Department of Aquaculture and Fisheries, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Ilorin where they were divided into four groups (4 fish per group) and each group was slaughtered (following University Ilorin ethical guideline on animal welfare) using the various slaughtering methods including: percussive stunning, salt stunning, ice slurry asphyxia and electrical stunning methods.

Percussive stunning was performed using the method of Gatica *et al.* (2010) by applying blow to the fish head. Salt stunning was performed using the method of Ayelaja (2019) by adding 20 g table salt/kg fish for 2 min. Ice asphyxia was performed using the method of Acerete *et al.* (2008) by immersion of fish in chilled water (2–4 °C), fish/ice ratio was 1:1. Electroshock was performed using our constructed fish electric stunning machine which work by passing 230vac electricity through an input electrical network circuit to 30 Amps transformer so as to step up the 230vac to 760vac output and the high frequency capacitor was used to filter and strengthen the high voltage so as to maintain the output constant high voltage. This fish stunning machine effective within the time frame of 3minutes which make fish unconscious or dead.

Treatments and experimental design

The experiment was completely randomized design comprising of four slaughtering methods:

1) — percussive stunning (2) salt stunning

(3) ice asphyxia (4) electro shock each replicated thrice

Measurement of pH and rigor index

The muscle pH and rigor index (stiffening of fish muscle) of the differently slaughtered fish were measured. The pH was measured by inserting a pH probe (Checker 200) into the upper mass of the fillet, just behind the head, and the rigor index was calculated as $[(L0-L3)/L0] \times 100$ (Erikson 2001), where L0 is the vertical drop (cm) of the tail, measured when the anterior half of the full length of the fish is placed on the edge of a table at the time of death, and L3 is the vertical drop measured 30 minutes later. Both measurements were made at the time of death (immediately fish stop breathing) and after every 30 mins at ambient temperatures ($27 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$).

Blood sampling and analytical procedures

Two blood samples were taken from each *C. gariepinus* in less than a minute, to avoid any changes in the variables induced by handling. The first sample was taken into a tube containing sodium fluoride to obtain plasma for the determination of glucose and lactate concentrations, and the second was collected without anticoagulant to obtain serum for determination of the concentrations of cortisol, sodium, urea and chloride and osmolality. Both samples were stored at -20°C for later analysis.

Glucose concentration was determined spectrophotometrically by the glucose oxidase/p-aminophenazone method, without deproteinisation. The lactate concentration was also determined spectrophotometrically by means of an enzymatic colorimetric method. Serum

sodium (Na) concentration was determined with a Perkin-Elmer 238 atomic absorption spectrophotometer. Urea and chlorides were determined colorimetrically by the glutamate dehydrogenase enzymatic method and the tripyriditiazine method, respectively, on a Cobas Mira Extra spectrophotometer (Roche). Urea nitrogen (N) was calculated as urea/2.14 and used to calculate serum osmolality from the formula of Holmes (1962).

mosmol/kg = 1.86 Na x Glucose x Urea nitrogen

(18) (2.8)

Cortisol was determined by means of a radioimmunoassay

Statistical Analysis

The pH and rigor mortis data were subjected to descriptive statistics (mean) and virtual analysis (bar chart) while the blood parameters data were subjected analysis of variance (ANOVA) using F-test to determine the treatments level of significance, and treatment means were separated using Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT) at 95% confidence value ($p < 0.05$).

RESULTS

The result on Figure 1 indicates that pH of heteroclaris slaughtered, fish stunned using percussive stunning had the highest pH (7.15) while fish stunned using ice slurry asphyxia had a pH of (7.0) and that stunned with salt had a pH of 6.9.

Figure 1: pH of Heteroclaris slaughtered with four different slaughtering methods

The result of the rigor mortis (Figure 2) show irregular pattern as the variation in the muscle curvature of heteroclaris does not follow a regular pattern.

Heteroclaris Rigor mortis between 0-12 hours using various slaughtering methods

Figure 2: Curvature of the tail measurement of *Heteroclaris* slaughtered with four different slaughtering methods

Table 1: Blood parameters of *Heteroclaris* slaughtered using different methods

Fish Stunning method	Urea (mM)	Glucose (mg/dl)	Sodium (mM)	Chloride (mM)	Potassium (mM)	Osmolality (Osm/kg)	Lactate (mg/dl)	Cortisol (ng/ml)
Percussive stunning	3.55±0.07 ^a	4.75±0.63 ^a	1.50±1.34 ^a	94.50±7.77 ^a	5.05±0.35 ^a	195.50±27.57 ^a	39.55±5.09 ^a	5.80±0.14 ^d
Salt stunning	4.30±0.14 ^b	3.30±0.56 ^a	1.09±2.82 ^a	98.00±2.82 ^a	6.35±2.61 ^a	225.50±6.36 ^a	40.47±1.64 ^a	7.69±0.13 ^c
Ice slurry asphyxi	4.85±0.07 ^c	7.40±1.27 ^b	1.09±1.69 ^a	81.00±2.68 ^a	3.80±2.26 ^a	232.50±26.16 ^a	28.97±1.53 ^a	8.61 ±0.07 ^a
Electrical stunning	3.50±0.00 ^a	4.35±0.35 ^a	1.12±3.81 ^a	85.00±0.00 ^a	4.45±1.90 ^a	196.00±22.62 ^a	41.12±4.12 ^a	8.55±0.05 ^b

Values in the same column with different superscripts are significantly different $p < 0.05$

The result of the blood parameters of heteroclaris slaughtered using different slaughtering methods (Table 1) indicate that there was no significant difference in the sodium, chloride, potassium, osmolality and lactate of the fish when slaughtered using the various slaughtering methods. However, the glucose, cortisol and urea of heteroclaris

slaughtered using ice slurry asphyxia was significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher when compared with other slaughtering methods used.

Discussion

It was found that the pH of heteroclaris slaughtered, fish stunned using percussive stunning had the highest pH (7.15) while fish

stunned using ice slurry asphyxia had a pH of (7.0) and that stunned with salt had a pH of 6.9. The variation in the pH of heteroclaris shows the degree of stress each stunning method impacted on the fish as the relationship between stress and the properties of fish flesh is usually related to the extent of muscle metabolites depletion (Pottinger, 2001). However the pH range of 6.9 – 7.15 recorded in this study is still within the normal range for farmed fish (Olsen and Elvevoll, 2010). One of the most accepted way of measuring primary responses to stress in fish is the increase in plasma cortisol and glucose (Barton, 2002). In this study glucose, cortisol and urea of heteroclaris slaughtered using ice slurry asphyxia was significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher when compared with other slaughtering methods employed. This is similar to the result of Acerete *et al.* (2009) in their study of comparison of two stunning/slaughtering methods on stress response and quality indicators of European sea bass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*) where it was reported that ice asphyxia produced a five-fold increase in glucose levels of fish while other methods studied only produced a 1.5–1.7-fold increase,

also cortisol levels increased 8-fold after the application of ice asphyxia whereas other slaughtering methods provoked a 5-fold increase. Rotllant *et al.* (2001) equally stated that plasma glucose values is an indicator of fish catabolic response after stress. If minimizing stress in fish so as to achieve good raw material (raw fish) for our desired fish products, it is important to adopt methods other than ice slurring asphyxia for stunning fish. This is in line with the opinion of Acerete *et al.* (2009) who stated that methods that make fish less sensitive to stressful procedures prior to the actual death should be employed in fish slaughtering to minimize fish suffering during slaughtering.

Conclusion

This study shows that the various slaughtering methods impacted some stress on heteroclaris but ice slurry asphyxia impacted the most severe stress. However, the values obtained for the pH and blood variables in this study indicate that the fish flesh is of good quality irrespective of the slaughtering method employed.

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